

Aphanothece sp. (2×10^6 /g), *Nostoc* (1.3×10^5 /g), and *Calothrix* sp. (4×10^4 /g).

Twenty-eight days after inoculation (30 days after transplanting [DT]), floating colonies were harvested and fresh weight, dry weight, and N content determined. The same BGA developed in inoculated and noninoculated plots, *Aphanothece* sp. being dominant. BGA harvested from control plots and inoculated plots were combined and redistributed evenly in the BGA-treated plots after these were drained. The following day (31 DT), the algal material was incorporated with a rotary weeder. Thirty days later (60 DT) the procedure was repeated. At maturity, grain and straw yield and grain protein content were measured.

Thirty days after transplanting, the biomass of mucilaginous BGA in inoculated plots was about twice that in the control (see table). *Aphanothece* was dominant in all plots, giving the BGA biomass a high water content (99.4%). Fresh weight biomasses of 18.7 and 33.0 t/ha produced only 1.5 and 2.6 kg N/ha.

Incorporating mucilaginous BGA in the surface soil negatively affected further development of BGA, as shown at 60 DT by a BGA biomass about 10 times lower in treated plots than in the control. At this time *Nostoc* sp. and *Aphanothece* sp. dominated.

BGA biomass produced in the plots, BGA biomass incorporated in treated plots, and rice yield.^a

			Produced in control (A)	Produced in BGA-treated (B)	Level of significance of the difference (A - B)	Incorporated in BGA-treated plots (A + B)
BGA biomass	30 DT	fw (t/ha)	18.7	33.0	10%	51.7
		dw (kg/ha)	74.8	132.0	10%	206.8
		N (kg/ha)	1.5	2.64	10%	4.8
	60 DT	fw (t/ha)	7.5	0.6	1%	8.1
		dw (kg/ha)	75.2	6.2	1%	81.5
		N (kg/ha)	1.72	0.14	1%	1.86
	30 DT + 60 DT	fw (26.2)	26.2	33.6	ns	59.8
		dw (kg/ha)	149.9	138.2	ns	288.1
		N (kg/ha)	3.22	2.78	ns	6.0
Rice yield	Grain t/ha	3.24 ± 0.29	3.31 ± 0.20	ns		
	straw t/ha	2.41 ± 0.21	2.38 ± 0.14	ns		
	protein % dw	1.45 ± 0.06	1.41 ± 0.06	ns		

^aEach value is the average of eight replications. fw = fresh weight, dw = dry weight.

Productivity in the control, in terms of dry weight and N, was similar during the 1st and 2d months of growth. Total productivity (sum of biomasses harvested at 30 and 60 DT) was similar in control and BGA-treated plots, the higher productivity in treated plots during the 1st month of growth being balanced by lower productivity during the 2d. From 60 DT to harvest, biomass of mucilaginous BGA was very low.

Total BGA biomass incorporated in treated plots was equivalent to 60 t fresh weight/ha (52 t at 30 DT and 8 at 60 DT), corresponding to only 6 kg N (4.14 at 30 DT and 1.86 at 60 DT). Previous experi-

ments had shown that about 20-30% of the N of incorporated BGA is available to the plant. This suggests that in the present experiment about 2 kg N was available to the plant, which was not enough to significantly increase the yield in treated plots.

Correlation between the different variables measured in the 8 replications of the control and BGA-treated plots were significant only for grain and straw yield. The absence of correlation between BGA biomass produced in control plots and rice yield indicates that N and growth-promoting substances exuded by the algae, if any, did not affect rice growth. □

Azolla diseases in Manipur, India

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Azolla (*A. pinnata*) is often inoculated immediately after Jul transplanting in northeast India. We surveyed azolla diseases to determine causes of azolla decline at or shortly before inoculation. Two disease pathogens were isolated: *Rhizoctonia solani* Kuhn and *Sclerotinia sclerotiorum* (Lib.) de Bary. *S. sclerotiorum* for the first time in Manipur. *R. solani* was found in 18 of 20 villages and *S. sclerotiorum* in 7 of 20. Because of the occurrence of *R. solani*, azolla

inoculation should be restricted in Manipur Valley rice fields because diseased azolla may be a primary inoculum for rice sheath blight disease. □

Influence of moisture regime on total biomass production of rice

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A simulated field experiment was conducted to determine the influence of moisture regime on biomass production of rice. The experiment was under a vinyl roof at TATC, Japan, in 1982 wet season. The experiment was in a factorial randomized complete block design in 4 bottomless, 2- × 1- × 0.6-m, rectangular

Total dry matter production of 2 rices at Tsukuba, Japan.

Variety	Dry matter production (g/hill) at moisture regime (%) of			
	40	60	80	100
Century Patna	16	19	18	20
Nihonbare	7	11	14	14

CD at 5% level for varieties × treatments 2